

Proposal of an effort-benefit diagram to compare unit and room air-change rates applied to a literature review

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ABSTRACT

The main task of every ventilation system is to dilute and extract pollutants from indoor air, most importantly in occupied space. This is usually achieved by exchanging polluted indoor air with less polluted outdoor air. In the case of a mechanical ventilation system, this process requires a fan power to be provided which is approximately proportional to the power of three to the resulting airflow. Because of this, reducing the necessary airflow to be provided by the ventilation unit e.g., by 10% would lead to a reduced power supply of about 27%. Vice versa, a necessary increase of 10% of the airflow provided by the unit, would result in an increased power supply of about 33%. To determine whether a reduced unit airflow is feasible or an increase in unit airflow is required, it is important to evaluate the ventilation efficiency for the occupied zone and any other zone with certain air change rate requirements. Unfortunately, this evaluation process is time-consuming as well as labour-intensive and can't be done for every indoor zone separately yet. However, for those situations where it has been performed, a common procedure for comparing them in a comprehensible graphical way would be helpful. This paper proposes a diagram to visualize how efficiently certain ventilation systems provide their unit air change rate as a room air change rate. As characteristic physical limits and isolines the values for ideal mixed ventilation and plug flow are included as well. Furthermore, the diagram has been applied to visualize air change rates from a literature review. The overview indicates, other than often assumed, real buildings do not necessarily reach ideally mixed ventilation. Pointing out that, it must be admitted as well, that currently the available data for such a comparison is often not based on a uniform measurement and evaluation procedure. Nevertheless, the proposed diagram can be a useful tool to communicate the air exchange performance of ventilation systems.

KEYWORDS

air change rate, air change efficiency, literature review

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the challenges we all face because of climate change, the building sector needs to contribute to energy savings by more airtight building envelopes combined with controlled ventilation systems. To keep the required power consumption of these systems as low as possible, it is essential to strive for a high ventilation or air change efficiency. However, this requires awareness in the design-phase of building of the fact that it is not sufficient to only move air, but also assure "fresh" or better younger air is provided where it is actually needed. Vice versa, a ventilation system has to efficiently extract polluted, or older air from the sources of these pollutants. Unfortunately, in practice, it is often assumed unit air change rates according to Equation (1) are equal to the air change rate present in any point within a ventilated space. This assumption is, for example, implicitly made in the German standard DIN 1946-6, which

means every ventilation system reaches by default the air change efficiency of ideal mixed ventilation or $\varepsilon_j^a = 50\%$. This is problematic because with such an assumption, there is no motivation to further improve the most relevant characteristic of a ventilation system.

$$n_j = \frac{\dot{V}_j}{V_j} = \frac{1}{\tau_j} \quad (1)$$

n_j	Nominal air change rate of a system j	$[\text{h}^{-1}]$
\dot{V}_j	Effective volume flow for a ventilated system j to exchange the air	$[\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}]$
V_j	Entire volume of the system j to be ventilated	$[\text{m}^3]$
τ_j	Nominal time constant of the system j as a characteristic statistical measure for the time air spends at least within that system	$[\text{h}]$

2 THEORY

To better understand the theoretical background of air change efficiency, it helps to imagine a simplified real room like in Figure 1. Most importantly, a real indoor space cannot be ideally mixed, rather it can be viewed as a more or less coarse or fine discretized mesh of zones filled with air of different ages which interact with each other.

Figure 1: Simplified sketch of a ventilated room with various air ages, where the exhaust catches air of some room average air age. A fraction of older air is stagnating in few regions of the indoor space (Auerswald 2023).

The assumption of mixed ventilation means that the average air age $\langle \bar{\alpha} \rangle_j$ of all locations over the whole space equals the nominal time constant τ_j of that space. The condition of ideal mixed ventilation is a theoretical reference condition, where every location or zone x_i has that average air age ($\bar{\alpha}(x_i) = \langle \bar{\alpha} \rangle_j = \tau_j$, $\varepsilon_j^a = 50\%$). The other two theoretical reference conditions are complete short-cut ($\varepsilon_j^a = 0\%$), where the air age in every indoor location is infinity ($\bar{\alpha}(x_i) = \infty$). And plug-flow ($\varepsilon_j^a = 100\%$), where the air crosses the indoor space on the most direct path from supply to exhaust without leaving a single location unventilated. The air age $\bar{\alpha}(x_i)$ under plug flow conditions increases linearly from 0 at the supply to τ_j at the exhaust, which means the average air age is $\langle \bar{\alpha} \rangle_j = 0,5 \cdot \tau_j$. With this said, the definition of the absolute air change efficiency ε_j^a follows than Equation (2) (Skåret 1986; Mundt and Mathisen 2004; Sandberg and Sjöberg 1983; Sandberg 1981).

$$\varepsilon_j^a = \frac{\tau_j}{\langle \bar{t}_j \rangle} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\tau_j}{\langle \bar{\alpha}_j \rangle} = \frac{1}{1 + \mu_2^*(\tau_j)} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle \bar{n}_j \rangle}{n_j} = \frac{\langle \bar{n}_{e,j} \rangle}{n_j} \quad (2)$$

ε_j^a	Absolute air change efficiency of a system j	[-]
τ_j	Nominal time constant of the system j as a characteristic statistical measure for the time air spends at least within that system	[h]
$\langle \bar{t}_j \rangle$	Average residence time of air within the system j or air age in the exhaust plane of that system	[h]
$\langle \bar{\alpha}_j \rangle$	Average air age within the system j	[h]
$\mu_2^*(\tau_j)$	Dimensionless second order central moment or dimensionless variance of the statistical distribution of residence times outside the system	[-]
$\langle \bar{n}_j \rangle$	Average room air change rate	[h ⁻¹]
n_j	Nominal air change rate of a system j	[h ⁻¹]
$\langle \bar{n}_{e,j} \rangle$	Average room air change rate in the exhaust plane of the system j	[h ⁻¹]

However, often it is neither relevant nor practically feasible to measure or otherwise evaluate the absolute air change efficiency. One example is here air volumes, which are enclosed by furniture. Relevant for the air exchange is mostly the zone occupied by persons. In order to reduce the complex reality and to consider the relevance of various zone for the use cases of the indoor space, it is helpful to set up a model which discretizes an indoor space into subsystems. With this in mind, it is logical to define a relative air change efficiency $\langle \varepsilon_j^a \rangle_i$ for a subsystem i inside the system j , according to Equation (3).

$$\langle \varepsilon_j^a \rangle_i = \frac{\tau_j}{\langle \bar{t}_j \rangle_i} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\tau_j}{\langle \bar{\alpha}_j \rangle_i} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle \bar{n}_j \rangle_i}{n_j} = \frac{\langle \bar{n}_{e,j} \rangle_i}{n_j} \quad (3)$$

$\langle \varepsilon_j^a \rangle_i$	Relative air change efficiency of a subsystem i in j	[-]
$\langle \bar{t}_j \rangle_i$	Average residence time of air within the subsystem i or air age in the exhaust plane of that subsystem	[h]
$\langle \bar{\alpha}_j \rangle_i$	Average air age within the subsystem i in j	[h]
$\langle \bar{n}_j \rangle_i$	Average room air change rate in the subsystem i	[h ⁻¹]
$\langle \bar{n}_{e,j} \rangle_i$	Average room air change rate in the exhaust plane of the subsystem i	[h ⁻¹]

Since air change efficiencies are a ratio of the achieved room air change rate to the nominal air change rate provided by the ventilation unit, it can be seen as a ratio of the benefit in relation to the necessary effort.

3 EFFORT-BENEFIT DIAGRAM FOR THE AIR CHANGE EFFICIENCY

Even though the evaluation of the air change efficiencies provides a method to quantify the performance of a ventilation system's capability to exchange indoor air, it is rarely used. The reason for this is the effort it takes to measure or simulate it. Also, because of the wide range of individual definitions for $\langle \varepsilon_j^a \rangle_i$ and even sometimes an unclear differentiation from the absolute air change efficiency, ε_j^a makes it difficult to further optimize existing ventilation system configurations. However, for those cases where the air change efficiency has been, and more importantly, will be evaluated, the effort-benefit-diagram for ventilation systems in Figure 2 can be a graphical method to reduce the burden of comparing different ventilation systems.

Furthermore, the diagram can be used to better communicate expectations from standards and regulations for ventilation systems.

Figure 2: Effort-benefit-diagram to visualize how efficiently a ventilation system provides a certain unit air change rate to the indoor space (Auerswald 2023).

The proposed diagram shows the ratio between the provided nominal or unit air change rate n_j in relation to the achieved room air change rate $\langle \bar{n}_j \rangle_i$. As a result, the diagonal isolines correspond to the relative air change efficiency $\langle \epsilon_j^a \rangle_i$. If $\langle \bar{n}_j \rangle_i$ covers the entire indoor space where n_j has been provided to, these lines become the isolines for ϵ_j^a . The two bold diagonal lines mark the values for the two reference cases, mixed ventilation and plug flow. The grey area is physically not possible to reach. If $\langle \bar{n}_j \rangle_i$ considers the requirement zone like the breathing level and Skåret's (1986) rules are considered, then efficient ventilation systems shall be designed for a relative air change efficiency $\langle \epsilon_j^a \rangle_i$ above the 50%-level. Additionally, the four vertical lines mark, as an example, the reference air change rates for the four indoor air quality expectation categories (IEQ) for a residential indoor space according to DIN EN 16798-1 (p. 56, table B.11). Since the standard suggest assuring an IEQ well above IV and to design for II, the area framed in bold lines in the diagram represents the target range for ventilation systems.

4 REVIEW OF RESULTS FOR THE RELATIVE AIR CHANGE EFFICIENCY

The following section provides an overview of measured and simulated air change efficiencies based on a literature review of scientific publications. Besides Google-Scholar the [AIVC Airbase](#) has been used to search for publications regarding ventilation efficiency, air change efficiency and air age evaluations. From the publications found the review considers only the reported points of interest inside the evaluated space. In the case of centralized ventilation systems with a continuous unidirectional flow, this data is sometimes provided additionally to

the easier accessible data in the exhaust ductwork, which leads to an absolute air change efficiency ε_j^a . Especially for decentralized systems with alternating flow, the accessibility between ε_j^a and $\langle \varepsilon_j^a \rangle_i$ is precisely the opposite, since there is no such location which continuously represents the exhaust duct only measurement data for the indoor space can be measured directly. For all presented data, it must be considered that there is no common practice how to exactly install the trace gas measurement equipment and how detailed the uncertainties of these evaluations shall be determined. Even though it shall be mentioned that there are the standards DIN EN ISO 12569 (2018) and DIN ISO 16000-8 (2008) which describe the tracer gas technique and how to calculate $\langle \bar{n}_j \rangle_i$ or $\langle \bar{a}_j \rangle_i$ respectively based on the measurement data. Of these two standards the second is more detailed. Based on the procedure in DIN ISO 16000-8 (2008) Auerswald (2023) presents an improved evaluation method for the measurement data and their uncertainties.

The first results on air change efficiency were published by Lidwell (1960), Sandberg (1981), and Skåret and Mathisen (1982). They transferred the tracer measurement technique to ventilation systems and tested it in the laboratory using nominal air change rates higher than those used in common practice for most buildings nowadays. Further investigations in a laboratory environment were carried out by Tomasi et al. (2013). A comprehensive summary of field measurement results in non-residential buildings (NRB) can be found in Fisk and Faulkner (1992). Data on the air change efficiency of residential ventilation systems are published by Merzkirch (2015), Mikola et al. (2017) and FGK e. V. (ed.) (2019). The classification of the studies considered by building and system type is listed in Table 1. Figure 3 visualizes the results of these studies by the introduced effort-benefit diagram.

Table 1: References for evaluations of the nominal and room air change rate, as well the resulting relative air change efficiencies. TS = test facility or simulation, NRB = non-residential building, H = including a heat source

Reference	Building type			System type	
	TS	NRB	flat	centralized	decentralized
				continuous	alternating
Sandberg (1981)	•			•	
Sandberg and Sjöberg (1983)	•			•	
Sandberg (1984)	•	•		•	
Fisk et al. (1985)		•		•	
Offermann and Int-Hout (1987)		•		•	
Fisk et al. (1988)		•		•	
Persily and Dols (1991)		•		•	
Fisk et al. (1991)	•			•	
Bauman et al. (1992)	•			•	
Persily et al. (1994)		•		•	•
Manz et al. (2000)	•, H				•
Olesen et al. (2011)	•, H			•	•
Tomasi et al. (2013)	•			•	•
Merzkirch (2015)			•	•	•
Mikola et al. (2017)			•		•, H
FGK e. V. (ed.) (2019)	•			•	•
Auerswald (2023)			•		•

5 CONCLUSIONS

From this small overview it can be concluded, that ventilation systems installed in buildings tend to not achieve at least mixed ventilation and thus do not satisfy Skåret's (1986) rules. Especially for those systems in residential buildings in Germany, it seems they tend to be under-

dimensioned. From references found and considered here, most of the systems which satisfied the requirement $\langle \varepsilon_j^a \rangle_i \geq 0.5$ are test facilities. This indicates that there may be a transfer gap from accepted scientific knowledge for the indoor air exchange to real-world buildings.

Figure 3: Effort-benefit-diagram applied to the comparison of data from a literature review about nominal air change rates to room air change rate, as well as the resulting air change efficiencies. Red = test facility, blue = non-residential building, green = residential building, orange = simulation (residential), triangle = centralized continuous system, rectangle = decentralized continuous system, circle = decentralized alternating system

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From indoor environmental quality point of view, sustainable buildings prioritize the quality of life and the wellbeing of the buildings' occupants and at the same time reduce negative environmental impacts. A building that, in its design, construction or operation, reduces negative impacts on our climate, also reduces their occupants' risk of related health problems and provides a more pleasant indoor environment, as well as increases occupants' satisfaction.

The conference organisers welcome contributions on the role of smart ventilation, building and ductwork airtightness and ventilative and resilient cooling on IEQ and health in sustainable buildings.

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Conference Organizers

INIVE (International Network for Information on Ventilation and Energy performance)

[INIVE](#) (International Network for Information on Ventilation and Energy Performance) was created in 2001. The main reason for founding INIVE was to set up a worldwide acting network of excellence in knowledge gathering and dissemination. At present, INIVE has as member organisations [Buildwise](#), [CETIAT](#), [Ghent University](#), [Fraunhofer-IBP](#), [KU Leuven](#)).

INIVE has multiple aims, including the collection and efficient storage of relevant information, providing guidance and identifying major trends, developing intelligent systems to provide the world of construction with useful knowledge in the area of energy efficiency, indoor environment, ventilation and airtightness of buildings. Building energy- and environmental performance regulations are another major area of interest for the INIVE members, especially in relation to the implementation of the European Energy Performance of Buildings Directive. With respect to the dissemination of information, INIVE aims for the widest possible distribution of information.

INIVE is coordinating and/or facilitating various international projects, e.g. the Air Infiltration and Ventilation Centre – [AIVC](#), [Dynastee](#), the Indoor Environmental Quality – Global Alliance – [IEQ-GA](#), the [TightVent Europe platform](#), and the [venticool](#) platform. INIVE has also coordinated the ASIEPI project (01/10/2007 – 31/03/2010) dealing with the evaluation of the implementation and impact of the EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, the QUALICHECK project and platform aiming towards improved compliance and quality of the works for better performing buildings, the European portal on Energy Efficiency – [BUILD UP](#) and the EPBD feasibility study 19a

AIVC

The AIVC (www.aivc.org) activities are supported by the following countries: Australia, Belgium, China, Denmark, France, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Republic of Korea, Spain, Sweden, UK and USA.

Created in 1979, the Air Infiltration and Ventilation Centre (www.aivc.org) is one of the projects/annexes running under the International Energy Agency's Energy in Buildings and Communities Programme. With the support of 16 member countries as well as key experts and associations (IEQ-GA, REHVA, IBPSA, ISIAQ), the AIVC offers industry and research organisations technical support aimed at better understanding the ventilation challenges and optimising energy efficient ventilation

Since 1980, the annual AIVC conferences have been the meeting point for presenting and discussing major developments and results regarding infiltration and ventilation in buildings. AIVC combines forces with the TightVent Europe and venticool platforms aiming at facilitating exchanges and progress on airtightness and ventilative cooling issues, which are major topics of this conference.

TightVent Europe

The [TightVent Europe](#) 'Building and Ductwork Airtightness Platform' was launched in January 2011. TightVent Europe aims at facilitating exchanges and progress on building and ductwork airtightness issues, including the organization of conferences, workshops and webinars. It fosters experience sharing as well as knowledge production and dissemination on practical issues such as specifications, design, execution, control, etc., taking advantage of the lessons learnt from pioneering work while keeping in mind the need for adequate ventilation. In September 2012, the TightVent Airtightness Associations Committee (TAAC) was also launched with the primary goal of promoting reliable testing/inspection and reporting procedures. TAAC gathers both TightVent partners and TAAC members (experts or representatives of airtightness testers in their countries).

TightVent Europe has been initiated by INIVE (International Network for Information on Ventilation and Energy Performance) with at present the financial and/or technical support of the following partners: [Lindab](#), [MEZ-TECHNIK](#), [Retrotec](#), [Acin Instrumenten](#), [BlowerDoor GmbH](#), BCCA, [dooApp](#), [Soudal](#), [Eurima](#), [Gonal](#), [SIGA](#) and [BPIE](#).

venticool

[venticool](#) is the international ventilative cooling platform launched in October 2012 to accelerate the uptake of ventilative cooling by raising awareness, sharing experience and steering research and development efforts in the field of ventilative cooling. In 2020, venticool decided to broaden its scope towards resilient ventilative cooling.

The platform supports better guidance for the appropriate implementation of resilient ventilative cooling strategies as well as adequate credit for such strategies in building regulations.

The platform philosophy is to pull resources together and to avoid duplicating efforts to maximize the impact of existing and new initiatives. venticool joins forces with international projects (in particular [IEA EBC Annex 62](#) (ventilative cooling) and, more recently, [IEA EBC](#)

[annex 80](#) (Resilient cooling for buildings)) and organizations with significant experience and/or well identified in the field of ventilation and thermal comfort like [AIVC](#) and [REHVA](#).

venticool was initiated by INIVE (International Network for Information on Ventilation and Energy Performance) with the financial and/or technical support of the following partners: NAVENTA, [Velux](#), [Reynaers Aluminium](#), [WindowMaster](#), [Active House](#), [CIBSE nvg](#), [Eurowindoor](#) and [REHVA](#).

Aalborg University

Aalborg University, founded in 1974, is Denmark's fifth largest university with 20.200 students. A young and international university with campuses in Aalborg, Esbjerg and Copenhagen, offering 76 undergraduate and 112 postgraduate studies with a real-world approach and provide world-class research.

Is divided into four faculties a) Technical Faculty of IT and Design, b) Faculty of Engineering and Science, c) Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, d) Faculty of Medicine.

Additionally, has a cross-cutting unit, AAU Innovation, tasked with strengthening entrepreneurship and innovation, and promoting the university's knowledge cooperation with society.

In 2018 an analysis by the elite US University MIT placed the AAU engineering programmes as the best in Europe and fourth best in the world. Respectively, in the QS World University Rankings by Subject, it is ranked 58th for Electrical Engineering and 25th in Petroleum Engineering worldwide. Aalborg University is very focused on developing engineers with experience from working with real companies in their semester projects. Also, focus is put on working in a team environment that develops the interpersonal skills, as well as team-working skills.

Additionally, in 2019 the Times Higher Education World University Rankins placed AAU at number 207, while among younger universities (under 50 years) AAU is number 18 in the world.

Common to all three campuses is AAU's strong focus on problem-based learning as well as interdisciplinarity and research-based innovation. Through strong interplay between staff and students and intense collaboration with public and private sectors, offers degree programmes with a real-world approach and provide world-class research.

AALBORG UNIVERSITY

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